

Rac-41

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-22-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	116	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 22 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/20/2021 3:45:43 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/5/2022 9:50:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.828	784361	50.11	64854
2	8.361	780859	49.89	53615

Asy-41

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-23-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	17	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 23 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/20/2021 4:07:59 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/5/2022 9:51:40 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.841	150698	9.31	12300
2	8.388	1467592	90.69	99377